

SMD Opportunities within the NASA SBIR Program

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NASA SBIR/STTR Program

sbir.nasa.gov

SBIR/STTR: Understanding the Basics

- **Small Business Innovation Research (SBIR)**
 - A set-aside program for small business to engage in Federal R&D – with potential for commercialization
 - Currently, 3.2% of federal agencies extramural R&D budgets for all agencies with a budget greater than \$100M per year
- **Small Business Technology Transfer (STTR)**
 - A sister set-aside program to facilitate cooperative R&D between small business concerns and U.S. research institutions – with potential for commercialization
 - Currently, 0.45% of the extramural research budget for all agencies with a budget greater than \$1B per year

VISION

A world where any entrepreneur can benefit humanity

MISSION

Empowering all small business communities to imagine, build, and utilize revolutionary technologies to drive NASA and the national economy to reach new heights

SMD Topic S17: Crosscutting Information Systems

- SMD engages in SBIR and leverages small business efforts to develop the directorate's technology portfolio.
 - One of seven major topics is **Crosscutting Information Systems (S17)** which solicits innovative and cutting-edge software solutions.
 - SMD annually reviews and tailors nominated “subtopics” to seek solutions for technology gaps.

Subtopic	Title	Center
S17.01	Technologies for Large-Scale Numerical Simulation	ARC
S17.02	Integrated Campaign and System Modeling	JPL
S17.03	Fault Management Technologies	GRC
S17.04	Application of Artificial Intelligence for Science Modeling and Instrumentation	GSFC

- PY23 as of now, 11 Phase I and 4 Phase II awards were made, representing a **~\$5 million portfolio investment** (~11% of SMD's share) from the NASA SBIR/STTR program (STMD).

EM Photonics, Inc

“A Scheduling-Based Framework for Efficient Massively Parallel Execution”

- 2016 until PII-E ended Feb 2020
- Infused into NASA program (CULA Tools now distributed by Nvidia, and NASA has purchased substantial Nvidia hardware)
- Resulted in new idea for NASA program (compressive computing could help NASA to achieve much greater efficiency on communication-bound application codes)
- CULA tools has reached more than 13,000 users worldwide (Oct 2023)

CULA | tools

SMD Software Success Stories

AutoNav Mark 4 (SBIR 2017)

Blue Sun Enterprises, Inc

Virtual machine language (VML) for autonomous spacecraft operation and exploration

- “NASA’s relationship with Blue Sun Enterprises, an engineering consulting firm based in Boulder, Colorado, has evolved over a decade with a series of SBIR awards which is pushing the boundaries of VML for space exploration”
- “To date, evolving versions of VML have been used on 14 missions.” (2018)

Thank You

- For SMD mission, programs, and projects, the SBIR program is a collaboration mechanism that can be strategically used to infuse software technology at the small business scale into NASA.

The NASA SMD community is what makes the agency's SBIR/STTR program successful!

Questions?

Visit our website:
www.sbir.nasa.gov

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